

CarE-Service

**Circular economy business models
for innovative hybrid and electric mobility through
advanced reuse and remanufacturing technologies and services**

KPIs assessment compared to targets

(Deliverable 7.6)

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Executive Summary

This deliverable is the work performed under WP7 “Demonstration & LCA assessment” and reports the outcomes of task 7.6 “KPIs assessment compared to targets” with respect to month 24 of the project. It aims at demonstrating the updated quantitative analysis of KPIs formerly identified in Grant Agreement (GA), D1.1 and D1.3.

To achieve this goal, primary KPIs were extracted from different deliverables and accordingly categorized in the following six value chains:

- B2B business models
 - Battery reuse value chain
 - Metal reuse value chain
 - Techno-polymer reuse value chain
 - ICT Platform
 - SMMs
- B2C business model (car sharing/ renting services).

Afterwards, where possible KPIs were assessed considering the current industrial scenarios before the introduction of the business models and solutions.

D7.6 is an upgradable document which will be updated every 6 months according to the new findings and solutions on demonstration scenarios. This deliverable is the first periodical KPI assessment compared to targets. The next reports, intermediate and ex-post, will be delivered on M30 and 36.

List of Acronyms

AGV: Automated Guided Vehicle

B2B: Business to Business

B2C: Business to Consumer

GA: Grant agreement

ICE: Internal Combustion Engine

ICT: Information Communication
Technology

KPI: Key Performance Indicator

LCA: Life Cycle Assessment

SMMs: Smart Movable Modules

WP: Work Package

Table of ContentA vertical flow diagram with four circular nodes connected by lines. Each node contains a page number in a grey circle, and to its right is a rectangular box containing the chapter title. The nodes are connected by lines that form a zig-zag pattern: a diagonal line from the top-left to the first node, a vertical line from the first node to the second, a diagonal line from the second to the third, a vertical line from the third to the fourth, and a diagonal line from the fourth to the bottom-left.

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1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Scope and objectives

This deliverable consists the report of first KPI periodical assessment (ex-ante) compared to target as part of the task 7.6. The next reports intermediate and ex-post will be submitted on M30 and 36 respectively. It performs a quantitative analysis of the key performance indicators (KPIs) which have been identified earlier in CarE-Service Grant Agreement (GA), D1.1 and D1.3. The activities of this task includes the KPI estimation based upon the status of the industrial scenarios before the introduction of the developed business models and solutions.

With this goal, a logical framework was developed and KPIs were classified in to six value chains in two levels: business-to-business (B2B) and business-to-customer (B2C). The systematic quantification of the KPIs allows a proper evaluation on performance and functionality of the CarE-Service. It is worth mentioning that due to lockdown imposed by COVID 19 pandemic most of the activities related to development of the three recovery value chains of battery, metal and techno-polymer (WP5) and business model developments of SMMs technology (WP4) and ICT Platform (WP6) were delayed thus, almost all KPIs could not be assessed during the reporting period.

1.2 Deliverable structure

This deliverable is structured as follows:

- **Introduction:** primary the objective and scope of this deliverable is presented (section 1).
- **Methodology:** the method deployed to collect and exploit the data is explained (section 2).
- **Results:** the results regarding KPI assessment is depicted. (section 3)

2 METHODOLOGY

The methodology applied for quantitative analysis of KPI is comprised of two main activities:

- Data collection
- KPI quantification method

2.1 Data Collection:

Primary CNR as a leader, initiated the task by extracting all previously identified KPIs from D1.1, D1.3 and CarE-Service Grant Agreement. Subsequently, all KPIs were integrated and classified according to six value chains:

B2B business models:

- Battery recovery value chain,
- Metal recovery value chain,
- Techno polymer recovery value chain,
- SMMs,
- ICT platform.

B2C business model which refers to car sharing/ renting services.

Tables were the main instrument applied for systematic tracking of each KPI (Table 1).

Extracted from (GA/D1.1/D1.3)	Key Performance Indicator (KPI)	Proposed target

Table 1. Framework for KPI collection

2.2 KPI Quantification Method:

Given that this report is an ex-ante KPI quantitative analysis, it was significant to primarily identify which KPIs could be quantified at the current stage of the project and which will be assessed in later stages when the result of testing and validation are available or during the demonstrations phase. In pursuit of this goal, CNR initially identified the target value status of each KPI with respect to month 24 via two options:

- *Non-applicable*: the ones that couldn't be quantified at this stage and will be demonstrated in later stages (intermediate and ex-post stages, M30 and 36 respectively).
- *Updated estimation by month 24*: based on the current industrial scenarios an updated estimation could be presented.

Afterwards, the file was distributed among task partners via email. They were asked to check and validate the assigned value status as well as providing relevant data for KPI quantification. However, most partners stated that due to consequences of COVID 19 the KPIs cannot be assessed during this period. (Figure 1). With respect to B2C KPIs a meeting was also held to update the relevant KPIs.

• Figure 1. Methodology of KPI assessment compared to target

In the following all identified KPIs and their target value status based on different value chains are presented.

- **KPIs of Battery Value Chain**

The KPIs of battery value chain were collected from *D1.1 and Grant Agreement*. Due to three different demonstration cases of batteries, KPIs were also defined specifically regarding each one. The following presents the three demonstration cases:

- Stationary application of reusing batteries in solar panels systems.
- Re-use of cells in e-bikes for customers (e.g. weekend riders), and for companies (e.g. freight, distribution bikes).
- Use of recovered compounds from battery recycling process for other applications.

KPIs retrieved from Grant Agreement were also placed under the relevant demonstration cases.

- ***KPIs of stationary application of reusing batteries in solar panels systems***

The following table demonstrates a detailed list of KPIs with respect to application of re-use batteries in solar panels. According to Grant Agreement the target capacity of re-used batteries in solar panels should be 50% compared to its first life system.

As can be seen in Table 2, all KPIs will be quantified in the next periods.

NO	Extracted from	KPI title	Proposed Target	Target Value by Month 24
1	GA	Target capacity of re-used batteries	50% with respect to the first life system	Non applicable
2	GA/ D.1.1	Customer acceptance of re-assembled batteries	100%, verified by IASOL in later stages	Non applicable
3	D.1.1	Relative reliability of reused battery compared to new one	Same	Non applicable
4	D.1.1	Relative durability of reused battery compared to new one	80-90%	Non applicable
5	D.1.1	Relative design featured of the reused battery compared to new one	Same	Non applicable
6	D.1.1	Minimum number of batteries need to be tested for identifying the business model	>10	Non applicable
7	D.1.1	Number of solar panels systems for demonstration	Minimum 1	Non applicable
8	D.1.1	Reduction percentage in price of reused battery compared to new ones	More than 15-20% compared to the same	Non applicable
9	D.1.1	Relative quality percentage of reused parts compared to new parts	100%	Non applicable

10	D.1.1	Chance of upgrading possibility	very low <5%	Non applicable
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Table 2. KPIs for Stationary Application of Reusing Batteries in Solar Panels Systems

- **Re-use of cells in e-bikes for customers (e.g. weekend riders), and for companies (e.g. freight, distribution bikes).**

A detailed list of KPIs collected from *D1.1 and Grant Agreement* regarding re-use of cells in e-bike was prepared. 2 KPIs were extracted from Grant Agreement. According to Grant Agreement the regeneration rate of reusable cells through re-assembly declared to be 90%. Also, the time needed to discharge, dismantle, test and re-assemble the cell shall be less than 2 hours.

NO	Extracted from	KPI title	Proposed Target	Target Value by Month 24
1	GA	Regeneration rate for reusable cells by re-assembly.	90%	Non applicable
2	GA	Cells discharge, dismantling, testing and re-assembly time.	<2 hours	Non applicable
3	D.1.1	Relative reliability of reused cells compared to new one	More	Non applicable
4	D.1.1	Relative durability of reused cells compared to new one	More or similar depending on the case	Non applicable
5	D.1.1	Relative design featured of the reused cells compared to new one	Same	Non applicable
6	D.1.1	Minimum number of batteries tested for reuse of cells of low-demand batteries for customers (eg. weekend riders)	>15 for consumers >15 for businesses	Non applicable
7	D.1.1	Number of demonstrated batteries for customers	>10 for customers >10 for businesses	Non applicable
8	D.1.1	Reduction percentage in price of reused battery	More than 15-20% up to 2/3 even with better quality (to be confirmed by e-bike company in later stages) AVIC prediction shows in 2025: the price for new battery could be 150-300 \$/kwh while 50-150 \$/Kwh for reuse battery	Non applicable
9	D.1.1	Relative quality percentage of reused cells compared to new cells	More	Non applicable

10	D.1.1	Number of training modules to be designed for this demo-case	Minimum 1	Non applicable
11	D.1.1	Chance of upgrading possibility	Very high >90%	Non applicable

Table 3. KPIs for Re-use of Cells in e-bikes for Customers and Companies

- **Use of recovered compounds from battery recycling process for other applications.**

Following the full KPI list of battery recycling is presented. Most KPIs were collected from D1.1, except 2 from Grant Agreement. According to Grant Agreement the material recovered from battery recycling should be more than 70%.

NO	Extracted from	KPI title	Proposed Target	Target Value by Month 24
1	GA	Material recovery yield from battery recycling	>70%	Non applicable
2	GA	Customer acceptance of recovered Li and Co for pigments in coatings	Verified by Ferro in demonstration package	Non applicable
3	D.1.1	Relative reliability of recycled compounds compared to new one	Same	Non applicable
4	D.1.1	Relative durability of recycled compounds compared to new one	Same	Non applicable
5	D.1.1	Relative design featured of the recycled compounds compared to new one	Same, if not better	Non applicable
6	D.1.1	Minimum number of batteries tested	Around 5	Non applicable
7	D.1.1	Minimum number of recovered compounds	>2	Non applicable
8	D.1.1	Relative Price of recovered material (same as virgin material or cheaper or even there is the option of upgrading so it can be sold more expensive.)	If the same quality can be achieved, the price can be the same with 0% reduction. AVIC forecast to be verified: buying price of old battery by recycling at a price around 8-10 \$/Kwh (1200\$/ton) and value recovered from recycling will be in the range of 3000 to 4000 \$/tons or 20-25 \$/Kwh	Non applicable

Table 4. KPIs for Use of Recovered Compounds from Battery Recycling process

- **KPIs of Metal Value Chain**

The table below comprises the KPIs collected from *D1.1 and Grant Agreement* for the value chain of metal remanufacturing parts. According to the CarE-Service Grant Agreement, the market acceptability of re-manufactured automotive parts is assigned by 70%. Furthermore, rate of re-used structural parts via using detachable joining interfaces is defined as 25% and rate of re-formed metal parts has been specified as 20%. In the following Table 2 the list of all KPIs related to metal remanufacturing value chain are depicted.

NO	Extracted from	KPI title	Proposed Target	Target Value by Month 24
1	GA	Rate of re-used structural parts by using detachable joining interfaces.	25%	Non applicable
2	GA	Rate of re-formed metal parts.	20%	Non applicable
3	GA	Market acceptability of re-manufactured automotive parts	70% (Verified by production of outer skin automotive parts (i.e. a hood or roof) of FIAT 500e out of a part disassembled from another vehicle version or model)	Non applicable
4	D.1.1	Chance of upgrading	Even low for high-end big components	Non applicable
5	D.1.1	Relative reliability of remanufactured parts compared to new one	Same	Non applicable
6	D.1.1	Relative durability of remanufactured parts compared to new one	Same	Non applicable
7	D.1.1	Relative design featured of the remanufactured parts compared to new one	Same	Non applicable
8	D.1.1	Number of roof tops for testing reforming	>20	Non applicable
9	D.1.1	Number of metal parts for testing of joining system	3	Non applicable
10	D.1.1	Number of parts for testing of joining system	>20 for each (to be verified)	Non applicable
11	D.1.1	Reduction percentage in price of reused metal parts compared to new ones	10%, to be verified	Non applicable

12	D.1.1	Amount of waste in treatment processes	Same as the waste in the first production	Non applicable
13	D.1.1	Relative quality of reused parts compared to new parts	Same	Non applicable

Table 5. KPIs for the Remanufacturing Metal Parts

- **KPIs of Techno Polymer Value Chain**

Table 6 shows the KPIs derived from *D1.1 and Grant Agreement* for recovery of CarE-Service techno-polymer parts mainly through recycling. According to the Grant Agreement, market acceptability of re-manufactured parts is assigned as 70% and it will be verified by re-production of minimum 10 new parts type. Furthermore, it was defined that the re-use material concentration in re-processed products should be more than 30% and the recycling rate is assumed to be more than 98%. Following is the detail list of all KPIs identified for techno polymer recovery value chain. It is expected that no KPI could be assessed within the reporting period and most of them would be quantified during the demonstration phase.

NO.	Extracted from	KPI title	Proposed Target	Target Value by Month 24
1	GA	Re-used material concentration in re-processed products	>30%	Non applicable
2	GA	Market acceptability of re-manufactured parts	70%. Verified by re-production of at least 10 new parts type (dashboards structures, battery supports, office chair supports, customized design products).	Non applicable
3	GA	Pass tests	Tensile modulus 6200 MPa (ISO 527-2/1A), flexural modulus 8300 MPa (ISO 178), melting temperature (220° (ISO 11357-13), Automotive interior flammability 0mm/min (FMVSS302), Moisture absorption 2% (ISO 62), concerning mechanical, physical properties and flammability.	Non applicable
4	GA/ D.1.1	Percentage of recycled materials from the input material	Recycling rate >98%	Non applicable
5	D.1.1	Relative design feature of the recycled material compared to virgin material (e.g. color)	Same	Non applicable

6	D.1.1	Percentage of techno-polymer material after extrusion in each part that can be considered as the input amount to the recycling	100%	Non applicable
7	D.1.1	Time for visual inspection	<20 minutes	Non applicable
8	D.1.1	Time for chemical disruptive technique to recognize the polymer composition in laboratory (DSC)	<2 hours	Non applicable
9	D.1.1	Number of total components in car that are usable for techno-polymers recycling	5 to 20	Non applicable
10	D.1.1	Relative selling price of recycled material compared to virgin material	Non-predictable (To be verified by demonstration)	Non applicable
11	D.1.1	Chance of upgrading possibility	0%	Non applicable
12	D.1.1	Percentage of techno-polymer material after dismantling of the car in each part that can be considered as the input amount to the recycling	Non-predictable (To be verified by demonstration)	Non applicable
13	D.1.1	Relative durability of recycled material compared to virgin material	Non-predictable (To be verified by demonstration)	Non applicable
14	D.1.1	Relative reliability of recycled material compared to virgin material	Non-predictable (To be verified by demonstration)	Non applicable

Table 6. KPIs of Techno-polymer Parts Mainly Through Recycling

- **KPIs for Business Model of ICT platform**

In the following table all KPIs collected from D1.1 and D1.3 regarding business model of ICT platform are presented. As it is shown in the Table 7, for the first 9 KPIs no proposed target has been set as they could not be measured in the course of the CarE-Service project since in order to have a precise quantification of such variables a certain time period needs to be passed from project execution. Therefore, during the demonstration only a rough estimation of such KPIs would be provided. Furthermore, it is important to mention that none of the ICT platform KPIs are assessed during this reporting period as most of them could only be quantified during the demonstration M36.

NO.	Extracted from	KPI title	Proposed Target	Target Value by Month 24
1	D.1.3	Number of visitors		Non applicable
2	D.1.3	Number of visitors per module		Non applicable
3	D.1.3	Number of parts requested		Non applicable
4	D.1.3	Number of parts published		Non applicable
5	D.1.3	Number of batteries published		Non applicable
6	D.1.3	Number of rentals for the smart modules		Non applicable
7	D.1.3	Number of days for smart modules rental		Non applicable
8	D.1.3	ICT platform uptime		Non applicable
9	D.1.3	ICT platform average response time		Non applicable
10	D.1.1	No. of membership types	Minimum 2 (e.g. Gold & Silver)	Non applicable
11	D.1.1	No. of roles members can register	Minimum 3 (e.g. Buyer, seller, etc.)	Non applicable
12	D.1.1	No. of registered companies in each role during the course of the project	Minimum 1	Non applicable
13	D.1.1	Total No. of members enrolled in the platform during the CarE-Service project	20 (consortium partners and SG companies)	Non applicable
14	D.1.1	No. of members enrolled in the platform during the CarE-Service project leveraged by other H2020 projects	Minimum 5	Non applicable

Table 7. KPIs for the Business Model of ICT Platform

- **KPIs for Business Model of SMMs**

Following tables encompass the detailed list of KPIs for business model of CarE-Service Smart Movable Modules (SMMs) retrieved from *D1.1*, *D1.3* and *Grant Agreement*. In this regard, KPIs are divided in to three categories:

- KPIs which consider both disassembly SMMs as well as testing and certification SMMs (Table 8).
- KPIs distinctively identified for the disassembly SMM (1st SMM) Table 9.

- KPIs distinctively identified for the testing and certification SMMs (2nd SMM) Table 10.

Like ICT platform, KPIs of SMMs also could not be quantified during this reporting period as most of them would be measured during the demonstration at M36.

NO.	Extracted from	KPI title	Proposed Target	Target Value by Month 24
1	GA/ D.1.1	Acceptability of modules by human operators	>95%, verified by means of questionnaires	Non applicable
2	D.1.1	No. of potential applications for each component	Minimum 2	Non applicable
3	D.1.1	No. of tools for consumer reassurance of procedures	Minimum 1 (to be verified)	Non applicable
4	D.1.1	No. of the regional clusters identified for determining the number of SMMs needed in each cluster for large scale exploitation of the solution.	Minimum 4 cluster of regions (for each cluster one range estimation of number of SMMs will be estimated)	Non applicable

Table 8. KPIs for the Business Model of CarE-Service Smart Movable Modules

- KPI's for SMM Disassembly

KPIs of SMM disassembly are divided in to four categories: General, KPI's for batteries, KPI's for techno polymers, KPI's for metal parts. (Table 9). Following table presents the detailed list of all KPIs.

NO.	Extracted from	KPI title	Proposed Target	Target Value by Month 24
General KPI's for SMM disassembly				
1	D.1.1	Capacity of 1 st Module	10 cars (to be verified)	Non applicable
2	GA/ D.1.1	Disassembly time(battery, metal parts and techno-polymer part dismantling)	<2 hours per car at least 3 experiments on a car model is anticipated for all parts of CarE-Service	Non applicable
KPI's for SMM disassembly of batteries				
3	D.1.3	Number of Battery pack removed per day	8 hour work/ 6 battery pack from no damaged car removed	Non applicable
4	D.1.3	Percentage of damaged battery during disassembly from the car	<10%	Non applicable
5	D.1.3	Time for reconfiguration of the module for a new model	1h with a trained worker in the case of screwing operations, 0.5h with a trained worker in the case of AGV. lifting device without automatic screwing	Non applicable

<i>KPI's for SMM disassembly of techno Polymers:</i>				
6	D.1.3	Number of elements removed per hour	Depending on the parts starting from 5 minutes per part e.g. handles and wipers, to 50 minutes for most complicated part	Non applicable
7	D.1.3	Time for reconfiguration of the module for a new part or a new model	15-20 min per part	Non applicable
8	D.1.3	Percentage of damaged parts (only parts that will be removed without destructive procedure)	<25%	Non applicable
<i>KPI's for SMM disassembly of metal parts</i>				
9	D.1.3	Number of parts removed per hour	Depending on the part starting from 10 minutes for side doors and front hood/ 20 minutes for bootlid. (this time will include the cooperation of the worker)	Non applicable
10	D.1.3	Time for reconfiguration of the module for a new part or a new model	15-20 minutes per part with a trained operator	Non applicable

Table 9. KPIs for the Business Model of Disassembly Smart Movable Modules (1st SMMs)

- **KPI's for SMM for testing and certification**

The testing and certification SMM aims at deciding if the part of a car could be re-used, recycled or would simply be a scrapped moreover, it would perform a testing and verification of the re-designed parts. The target value of KPIs of testing and certification SMMs have not been verified formerly thus, IMA has identified the relevant data regarding most of them. Also, for the first KPI, capacity of 2nd module, the target value is identified as the mean fraction of the remanufactured/recycled parts which means for example if the roof of a car is available after cutting it a fraction of the blank is still ready to be used thus, after the reforming process only a fraction of the fraction will be remained which is considered to be 66% of metal of the roof for a second life part.

The following table represents all KPIs identified for SMM of testing and certification, the updated estimation of such KPIs would be submitted during demonstration phase.

NO.	Extracted from	KPI title	Proposed Target	Target Value by Month 24
1	D.1.1	Capacity of 2 nd Module	The means of the fraction of part which is remained: 66% for metal parts, 40% for techno polymer parts, 50% for battery.	Non applicable
2	D.1.3	Cost of qualification (testing and certification)	To be verified in next stage	Non applicable

3	D.1.3	Personnel requirements for qualification (testing and certification)	Number of courses to be taken related to non-destructive testing and time of practice (e.g. examiner class II) and special trainings to work with electrical devices and testing machines	Non applicable
4	D.1.3	Throughput through the SMM	5 parts from one car to be evaluated per shift of 8h; e.g. calibration or referencing measurements	Non applicable
5	D.1.3	Time consumption per part (within the SMM)	Mean time to be 15min; for instance roof blank and wheel covers; 100% operator time	Non applicable

Table 10. KPIs for the Business Model of Testing and Certification Smart Movable Modules (2nd SMMs)

- **KPIs of B2C**

The following table demonstrates the KPIs for adoption for EV/HEV car sharing and renting services. Since some KPIs with reference to B2C business models might seem unclear primary their definitions are presented.

Vehicle utilisation rate: on average, European cars are parked 92% of the time (Ellen MacArthur Foundation, 2019). Thus, one of the main goal of car sharing companies is to increase the profit through maximizing vehicle utilisation. In pursuit of this goal, cars need to be utilized at least 60% of their total lifetime.

Charging stations at main transport hubs: the use of electric vehicle strongly relies on accessibility of charging stations; to this aim, at least one charging station with multiple charging points should be available at each transport hub.

Percentage discount versus regular parking payment: cost-effective parking lot is a significant requirement for car sharing service providers; hence, at least 10% discount on regular parking price is an acceptable support for car sharing companies.

Car models with different capacities: due to customers' needs car sharing companies should provide different car models with various capacities; for instance, a customer might carry a suitcase and need a large capacity car. In this regard, at least two different sizes ranging from small to large capacity cars should be available.

EV composition in fleets: car sharing companies should aim towards a regular shift from ICE cars to 100% electric vehicle composition since some governments have already declared that they will slow down the vehicle emissions by 2030.

NO.	Extracted from	KPI title	Proposed Target	Target Value by Month 24
1	Grant Agreement	Customer satisfaction rate, measured by specific questionnaires	70%. Customers experiencing new services at least 50 customers in at least two sample urban areas.	Non applicable
2	D.1.1	Vehicle utilization rate	At least 60% of total life time	Non applicable

3	D.1.1	Charging station at main transport hub	Min. one charging station with multiple charging points at each transport hub	Updated estimation by month 24
4	D.1.1	Percentage discount vs. regular parking payment	At least 10% of regular price	Updated estimation by month 24
5	D.1.1	Number of car models with different capacities	At least two different car capacities: small and large	Updated estimation by month 24
6	D.1.1	EV composition in fleet	100% EV fleet composition by 2030	Updated estimation by month 24

Table 11. B2C KPIs

3 RESULTS AND UPDATES

Broadly speaking, due to the lockdown imposed by the COVID-19 pandemic the activities of this task were slowed down. To be more specific, as the laboratories were closed, the activities related to the developing of the three recovery value chain of battery, metal and techno-polymer (WP5) and development of the business model of SMMs technology (WP4) and ICT Platform (WP6) were delayed. Therefore, none of the KPIs regarding the mentioned value chains could be quantified during this reporting period.

Thus, at this stage solely the KPI of B2C have been assessed. In the following table the KPIs which have been updated by EVAI within this reporting period are shown.

NO.	Extracted from	KPI title	Proposed Target	Target Value by Month 24
1	D.1.1	Charging station at main transport hub	Min. one charging station with multiple charging points at each transport hub	According to EVAI the 30% of FERROVIENORD (Lombardy Region) railway hubs has an electric infrastructure.
2	D.1.1	Percentage discount vs. regular parking payment	At least 10% of regular price	According to deliverable 2.1, the parking lots installed in the railways stations of EVAI for EV car sharing will be 100% free of charge
3	D.1.1	Number of car models with different capacities	At least two different car capacities: small and large	EVAI fleet includes 2 different models: one small capacity and one medium capacity
4	D.1.1	EV composition in fleet	100% EV fleet composition by 2030	EVAI fleet composition is composed of 90% EV

Table 12. B2C KPIs updates based on M24.

References

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